

CARBON FIBRE COMPOSITE REINFORCEMENT OF ALUMINIUM SUPERSTRUCTURE

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ABSTRACT

Work is in progress to develop a bonded composite reinforcement that conforms to the contour of the uneven aluminium-alloy deck of the Royal Australian Navy FFG-7 class frigate superstructure. This paper gives an overview of the project to date, dealing with the design of the reinforcement; the materials development and characterisation of the matrix, composite and adhesive bond; the method developed to allow rapid *in-situ* application of the reinforcement; the evaluation of a representative joint and the large scale composite fabrication, including *in-situ* post-cure and composite protection.

Keywords: Composite reinforcement, adhesive bonding, in-situ application.

1. INTRODUCTION

The aluminium-alloy superstructure of the US designed FFG-7 frigates, in operation with the Royal Australian Navy (RAN), Figure 1, have a serious fatigue cracking problem¹ in a region close to a transverse welded butt-joint in the necked midship upper-deck area. The cracking, which initiates from localised regions of high stress concentration, results from cyclic loading of the ship induced by wave action in heavy seas. The deck is significantly undulated and thus fit-up problems preclude the use of metal doublers, whether they be attached by welding, bolting or adhesive bonding. Also, more substantial solutions such as large-scale metal reinforcement using thick metal insert plates would be very expensive and may carry an unmanageable weight penalty.

Figure 1. Schematic drawing of US. designed FFG-7 class frigate in service with RAN

The application of carbon-fibre composite doublers bonded directly onto the ship's structure offers certain advantages over metal reinforcement. Carbon fibre has a much higher modulus than aluminium, is lightweight, will conform to an uneven plate contour and can be applied without the need to remove below deck equipment. Further, bonded reinforcement provides much improved load

transfer, is highly resistant to interface corrosion and avoids the weakened, heat-affected zone prevalent in welded metal repairs.

This paper briefly summarizes the development of a bonded carbon-fibre composite doubler to reinforce the aluminium alloy deck of the RAN FFG-7 frigate superstructure. The purpose of the reinforcement (5 m long by 1 m wide) is to reduce the localised cyclic stresses which cause a cracking problem in the region of a weld between 9.53 mm and 6.37 mm thick aluminium alloy (5456) plates. A taper of approximately 15° is present at the weld resulting from the weld dressing operation. A detailed project description is given in Reference 2.

2. COMPOSITE REINFORCEMENT DESIGN

The objective is to form and bond the fibre composite patches to the uneven contour of the aluminium plate in the region of the weld as illustrated in Figure 2. Two bonding options were considered: a) simultaneously with the composite forming process using a single resin system for the wet lay-up procedure, or b) as a separate operation requiring pre-fabrication of the reinforcement followed by adhesive bonding. The first approach requires fewer processing steps, offers simple fabrication of a reinforcement that conforms to the contour of the deck surface and importantly, there could be no compatibility problems between the adhesive resin and the composite matrix. The second approach requires a pre-cured reinforcement that matches exactly the deck contour to allow effective adhesive bonding. It was decided to adopt the simpler *in-situ* wet lay-up resin application process.

Figure 2. Necked, midships region of the frigate superstructure

For an *in-situ* lay-up process the selected resin system must allow ambient temperature cure, possess high toughness (to resist the peel component in the adhesive layer), have sufficiently low viscosity for good fibre wet-out and offer reasonable processing flexibility, particularly pot life.

Bond strength and durability is very sensitive to adherend surface treatment. On the basis of previous experience^{3,4} a simple treatment was selected which involved mechanical abrasion of the surface followed by application of a suitable silane solution.

Because of their excellent mechanical properties, carbon fibres were chosen for the reinforcement. Since the cyclic load at the region of high stress concentration is directed along the axis of the ship only unidirectional fibres were used.

3. MATERIALS DEVELOPMENT

3.1. Laminating Resin Selection

The commercially available, ambient-temperature curing, laminating-resin systems considered for this project are given in Table 1. Initial studies, using a simple but effective adhesive T-peel test ⁵ (which is indicative of resin toughness), revealed an unacceptably low peel strength (20-25 N/25.4 mm) for all the resins investigated. The toughness of the ambient temperature cured epoxy resins was partially improved by the addition of certain toughening agents but after a post-cure at elevated temperature this improvement was lost. Attempts to increase the toughness of the vinyl-ester resins also failed, except in the case of Derakane 8084. This resin showed a significant improvement after the addition of B. F. Goodrich vinyl-terminated butadiene acrylonitrile rubber (VTBN), which was retained after an elevated temperature post-cure. At the 5-10% level of VTBN rubber excellent peel strengths exceeding 65 N/25.4 mm were achieved, Figure 3.

Resin System	Modifier	Manufacturer
Epoxy resin LY1927	-	Ciba Geigy (UK)
Epoxy resin XB3052	-	Ciba Geigy (Aust.)
Aropol 6700	Urethane Acrylate	Chemplex (Aust.)
Derakane 411	-	DOW Chemical (Aust)
Derakane 8084	CTBN Rubber	DOW Chemical (USA)

Table 1. Commercial resin systems considered for this project

Figure 3. Effect of modifiers on peel strength of epoxy and vinyl ester resins.

The enhancement in toughness was accompanied by only a slight drop in glass transition temperature as measured by Dynamic Mechanical Thermal Analysis (DMTA). DMTA also indicated a negligible drop in modulus for the rubber-modified resin at the expected maximum service temperature of 75°C. Since VTBN rubber has a high viscosity (40,000 Cps) it was decided a 5% concentration of rubber that provided good toughness and a negligible increase in viscosity would be used. Also, single-overlap adhesive shear tests ⁶ indicated no decrease in shear strength of the Derakane 8084 resin after rubber modification.

Based on the above, it was decided to use Derakane 8084 modified with 5% VTBN as the resin system for producing and bonding the carbon fibre composite reinforcement.

3.2. Surface Treatment

The strength and durability of an adhesive bond requires optimized surface pre-treatment of the adherends. For this *in-situ* reinforcement application, only simple, non-toxic surface treatments for the aluminium alloy deck could be considered. Mechanical treatments, such as blasting the adherend surface with abrasive grit (eg. alumina or zirconia), enhance strength by increasing the available surface area for mechanical bonding. However, bond durability with the vinyl-ester adhesive is significantly improved by treating the grit-blasted surface with a 1% aqueous methacrylate silane solution. The silane is considered to chemically couple the adhesive to the oxide layer on the metal adherend surface ⁷. The bond durability of the rubber-modified vinyl-ester adhesive was assessed by performing a series of Boeing wedge tests ⁸ in which the specimens were exposed to hot/wet (50°C, 96% RH) and simulated marine environments (35°C, 5% salt fog). In both cases the bond durability was good with minimum crack extension during lengthy exposure.

3.3. Fibre Composite

A simple technique was required for *in-situ* manufacture and bonding of the composite doubler that would produce a composite of high quality (high fibre volume fraction and low porosity) with the desired geometry, closely matching the plate contour. A vacuum-bag technique was considered suitable providing even pressure over the contoured surface and isolating any noxious solvent or resin vapours from the operator. Further work showed that application of resin to selected layers of a multi-layer dry fibre lay-up produced a good quality, high fibre volume fraction composite under vacuum-bag conditions. The effect of matrix resin variation, fibre volume fraction, composite porosity and temperature change on the mechanical performance of the composite systems was evaluated. Test composite panels were fabricated using two vinyl-ester resins (commercial Derakane 8084 and VTBN rubber-modified Derakane 8084) and the epoxy resin XB3052. Torayca unidirectional carbon fibre cloth was used to fabricate the composites.

The mechanical properties ⁹ were found to be acceptable and unaffected by composite porosity. An increase in the carbon-fibre volume fraction caused the Flexural Strength (FS) and Flexural Modulus values to increase proportionally but the Interlaminar Shear Strength (ILSS) values were not affected. When comparing the carbon/epoxy to the carbon/vinyl-ester composites, it was found that the ILSS and FS values were slightly higher for the epoxy system. This may be explained in terms of the universally used sizing treatment for commercial carbon fibre which is epoxy-based.

4. DESIGN AND ANALYSIS OF A FATIGUE TEST SPECIMEN

To demonstrate that the reinforcement system was capable of producing a significant reduction in strain over the region of the weld and survive the fatigue stresses imposed on the region for a reasonable lifetime, an aluminium specimen, 1240 mm long and 100 mm wide, was manufactured to incorporate mid-length a change of thickness from 25 mm to 12.7 mm via a 15° taper, Figure 4.

The specimen was symmetrically reinforced with carbon fibre composite to avoid bending as it is assumed that the ship's structure will not allow significant out-of-plane movement of the deck. The mid-length taper is an idealised representation of both a dressed weld and a severe undulation of the deck plate.

Figure 4. Schematic diagram of test specimen showing position of electrical resistance strain gauges.

4.1. Finite-Element Analysis of the Test Specimen

A preliminary elastic finite-element (F-E) analysis of the test specimen was undertaken to determine the feasibility of the proposed repair scheme. The effectiveness of the repair was ascertained by considering the "reinforcing efficiency" of the doubler (the percentage reduction in strain achieved by the reinforcement), the composite transverse stress, and the adhesive peel and shear stress levels experienced in the region of the change in specimen thickness. The two-dimensional finite-element model of the test specimen is shown in Figure 5. Due to symmetry, only half of the specimen was modelled. Regions of potential high stress concentration are identified and labelled.

Figure 5. Two-dimensional F-E model of test specimen showing regions of high stress concentration.

Based on the approach taken by Molent et al ¹⁰, the design allowables are taken to be:

$$\tau_a < 26.7 \text{ MPa}, \sigma_a < 26.7 \text{ MPa}, \sigma_{xc} < 980 \text{ MPa}, \sigma_{yc} < 22.2 \text{ MPa}, \tau_c < 30.9 \text{ MPa}.$$

where the adhesive shear yield strength is τ_a , adhesive tensile yield strength is σ_a , the composite tensile strength is σ_{xc} , the composite transverse yield strength is σ_{yc} and the composite shear yield strength is τ_c .

Table 2 lists the estimated stresses at each of the critical regions illustrated in Figure 5 and thus indicates that the proposed repair appears to be feasible under static loading since none of the stress states exceed the design allowables.

Region No.	σ_x (MPa)	σ_y (MPa)	τ (MPa)
1	53.25	9.0	5.2
2	9.7	11.2	-3.6
3	100.6	12.0	14.8
4	1.4	-0.44	-1.7
5	-4.3	-8.2	-0.77
6	-3.8	-7.8	-0.33
7	4.8	0.51	2.2

Table 2. Stress levels in the critical regions of the reinforced specimen, illustrated in Figure 5, where σ_x is the tensile stress, σ_y is the normal stress and τ is the shear stress at the regions.

The analysis of the unreinforced specimen shows a maximum stress (σ_x) at the thin edge of the taper (region 1 in Figure 7) to be 110.1 MPa. When the reinforcement is applied, and the analysis repeated, the maximum stress reduces to 53.25 MPa. This implies a reinforcing efficiency of 51.2%. It therefore appears that the repair should be successful in reducing significantly the stress concentration at the thin edge of the taper without exceeding the static yield allowables of the reinforcing system.

4.2. Test Specimen Preparation

The aluminium alloy test specimen was surface treated as given in section 3.2. A scrim cloth was used to control the adhesive bond line to a thickness of approximately 0.1 mm and the 25 layer unidirectional carbon fibre/modified vinyl-ester composite was fabricated to reinforce both sides using the technique previously described. The effective patch length either side of the 15° step was 300 mm ending in a 3° taper over 120 mm, Figure 4. A pre-formed aluminium caul plate was employed to produce a flat and smooth surface finish.

The specimen was post-cured at approximately 60-70 °C for 5 hours and the resulting differential thermal expansion between the aluminium specimen and the carbon/vinyl-ester patches was minimised by fixing the specimen into an "anti-expansion frame" fitted with anti-buckling guides.

4.3. Mechanical Analysis of the Test Specimen

A detailed static strain survey of the reinforced specimen was conducted at ambient temperature in an Instron 500 kN servo-hydraulic testing machine at the peak fatigue stress in the superstructure region subject to cracking, which has been estimated to be 75.6 MPa. An average reinforcing efficiency of 56.2% was achieved which agrees well with the value computed by the finite-element analysis of 51.2%.

The fatigue life of the composite and adhesive system was assessed by dynamic cycling at ambient temperature under sinusoidal, constant amplitude loading. Electrical-resistance strain gauges were bonded onto the specimens to monitor strain on loading. Additional gauges were bonded to the reinforced specimen in the critical stepped end regions of the patch to monitor patch delamination or debonding during fatigue cycling, Figure 4. A computer-based data acquisition system was used to

monitor the test loads and record the strain readings of the loaded specimen during the test. The tension-compression cycling was carried out at 3 Hz and spanned specimen fatiguing at 91.2 kN (stress level of 75.6 MPa), 132.2 and 182.5 kN (the latter loading being equivalent to about 67% of the yield strength of the aluminium specimen in the thin section and twice the maximum expected stress level in the critical region of the superstructure). A total of approximately 100,000 cycles was completed before cracking of the aluminium in the test grips halted the experiment. Results indicated some relaxation in the output of only 4 strain gauges (bonded to the composite taper) which, upon visual and non-destructive evaluation (NDE) analysis, revealed a small composite interlaminar failure covering an area of approximately 2 cm². Recently, a second specimen of identical dimensions was tested under the same conditions at ambient temperature and also at 35°C. Again, the composite reinforcement performed extremely well showing no greater damage to that described above, even after 200,000 fatigue cycles.

5. FULL SCALE COMPOSITE REINFORCEMENT

A number of problems were encountered during the scale-up of the laboratory work to production of a full size composite reinforcement (5m long by 1m wide). These included post-cure of the carbon fibre composite, prevention of possible electrolytic corrosion between the two highly conductive materials (aluminium and carbon fibre) and physical and environmental protection of the composite reinforcement.

5.1. Composite Post-cure and Electrolytic Protection

Post-cure of the composite system was achieved by utilising the reinforcing carbon fibres as heater elements to heat and thus further advance the resin system. A current is passed through the fibre reinforcement and the electrical resistance of the fibres generated sufficient heat to post-cure the composite. The carbon fibre composite was isolated (and strongly bonded) from the aluminium substrate to prevent leakage of electrical current and thereby increase the efficiency of the heating system ¹¹. This isolation also suppressed the possibility of electrolytic corrosion between the aluminium and carbon fibre composite ¹².

This technique has been successfully demonstrated, on a quarter size scale, using a 25 layer carbon fibre composite (1.25m x 1m), bonded to a 6 mm thick aluminium plate (1.8m x 1.2m). A post-cure temperature exceeding 60°C was easily achieved during this application.

5.2. Composite Protection

In service, the composite reinforcement will be required to withstand the harsh marine environment whilst the ship is at sea. Due to its size and location, Figure 2, the reinforcement will require adequate protection against solar radiation and impact damage. A protective surface layer that readily accepts the ship's standard non-skid paint, will blend-in with its surroundings causing no obstruction to operators movements and allow easy surface water drainage was chosen. The protective layer must also prevent the ingress of water into the composite reinforcement as this could lead to irreversible hydrolysis of the matrix resin and consequent reduction in composite strength.

A selection of coating materials was evaluated using a standard drop weight test ¹³ followed by NDE to assess the damage. The effectiveness of two polyurethanes, modified vinyl-ester/glass and epoxy/glass composites was assessed from plots of impact energy versus observed debonded areas obtained by impacting 150 mm square specimens with an 8 mm radius tup. Although one of the polyurethanes gave the best performance, the presence of isocyanates in this product was considered

to be an unacceptable health hazard. The glass-reinforced modified vinyl-ester resin was found to be superior to both the other polyurethanes and the epoxy/glass.

6. CONCLUSION

Finite-element analysis has shown that composite reinforcement of the aluminium deck plate of a FFG-7 frigate should reduce the high stress concentration prevalent in the critical superstructure region. Using a multi-disciplinary approach including chemistry, materials science, mechanics and engineering, it has been demonstrated experimentally that an *in-situ* reinforcement can reduce stress by at least 50%, provide a strong and durable bond when exposed to simulated marine conditions and possess high resistance to composite damage in fatigue cycling at loads exceeding twice those normally experienced in service.

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